

TABLE 2. SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Zn-Co, Zn-Cu AND Zn-Ni
10 ml of 0.2M KBr = 10 ml of 0.2M KSCN = 20 ml of Hg(NO₃)₂

Amount of zinc taken, mg	Amount of metal taken, mg	Volume of 0.2M KBr used by zinc, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by Zn+M, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by metal, ml	Zinc found, mg	Metal found, mg.	% error	
							Zn	Metal
<i>Determination of Zn-Co</i>								
1.63	14.73	0.25	2.75	2.50	1.63	14.73	0.00	0.00
6.54	11.79	1.00	3.00	2.00	6.54	11.79	0.00	0.00
11.44	7.37	1.75	3.00	1.25	11.44	7.37	0.00	0.00
14.71	5.89	2.25	3.25	1.00	14.71	5.89	0.00	0.00
<i>Determination of Zn-Cu</i>								
19.61	1.59	3.00	3.25	0.25	19.61	1.59	0.00	0.00
13.07	6.35	2.00	3.00	1.00	13.07	6.35	0.00	0.00
8.17	9.53	1.25	2.75	1.50	8.17	9.53	0.00	0.00
4.90	13.71	0.75	2.75	2.00	4.90	13.71	0.00	0.00
<i>Determination of Zn-Ni</i>								
17.98	1.47	2.75	3.00	0.25	17.98	1.47	0.00	0.00
13.07	4.40	2.00	2.75	0.75	13.07	4.40	0.00	0.00
9.81	7.34	1.50	2.75	1.25	9.81	7.34	0.00	0.00
3.27	13.21	0.50	2.75	2.25	3.27	13.21	0.00	0.00

Volumetric determination of cadmium, zinc and palladium: To an aliquot of metal nitrate solution added isoquinoline solution and 10 ml. of 0.2M potassium bromide in case of cadmium and zinc, for palladium 10 ml of 0.1M potassium iodide was added. The proper pH were maintained. The volume was made upto 25 ml, allowed to stand for 10-15 min and filtered through Whatman no. 42 filter paper. The first few ml. of the filtrate were rejected, to 5 ml of the filtrate, added 10-15 ml of distilled water (adjusted the pH 3.0 in case of zinc and cadmium, in case of palladium there is no need of adjusting the pH but for better results instead of putting 10-15 ml of water, 10-15 ml of ethanol is to be added) 1-2 drops of the indicator and titrated with mercuric nitrate solution with the appearance of violet colour. The decrease in the concentration of bromide ions corresponded to zinc and cadmium while that of iodide ions corresponded to palladium. 2.81-22.48 mg of cadmium, 1.63-19.61 mg of zinc and 0.66-13.30 mg of palladium were determined with error not more than $\pm 0.01\%$ in any case.

Simultaneous determinations of Co-Cd, Cu-Cd, Ni-Cd, Co-Zn and Ni-Zn: These were found possible based upon the formation of isoquinoline halide and isoquinoline thiocyanate complexes. The results of these determinations are given in Tables 1 and 2.

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Role of Reactivity in Cupola Operation

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SINCE the carbon monoxide in stack gases of a cupola arise from the reaction of coke with carbon dioxide, according to the reaction $\text{CO}_2 + \text{C} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{CO}$, and also because different cokes have different reactivities towards carbon dioxide, it has often been assumed that the reactivity of coke towards carbon dioxide plays an important role in cupola operation.

Peter and coworkers^{1,2} have applied, to cupola operation, the principles of reaction kinetics of porous solids with gaseous substances. According to them, reaction in the combustion and lower part of the gasification zone, is controlled by boundary layer diffusion, in the top part of the gasification zone by pore diffusion, and in the preheating zone (the top part of the shaft) by chemical reaction. Since the gasification intensities in the chemical reaction region, are, by several magnitudes, smaller than those in the lower combustion and gasification regions, the former region is considered to be a relatively unimportant region, and for all practical purposes, it is

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the size distribution of coke and not its reactivity that influences the conversion of carbon dioxide to carbon monoxide.

In agreement with the above reasoning, it has been found by us that densite, a German synthetic fuel, well-known for its performance in the cupola, has a higher reactivity towards carbon dioxide at 1000°C than either a typical Australian or Durham foundry coke (Table 1).

TABLE I. SPECIFIC GASIFICATION RATES $\times 10^4$ (G/G D.A.F./MIN) OF AUSTRALIAN, DURHAM AND DENSITE FOUNDRY COKES WITH CARBON DIOXIDE AT 1000°C

Coke	Burn-off		
	20%	40%	60%
Australian	12.9	15.1	13.5
Durham	6.8	7.3	7.3
Densite	11.5	15.0	24.0

The reaction was carried out** in a furnace, whose temperature was raised in nitrogen to and maintained at 1000°C by a temperature controller supplied by Ether Inc. The cokes were contained in a quartz bucket suspended from a calibrated copper-beryllium spiral. The nitrogen was replaced by carbon dioxide (purified of traces of oxygen by passing over platinised asbestos), and the contraction of the spiral measured using a cathetometer fitted with a telescopic objective. The rates of gasification were calculated from the weight loss vs. time curves. The rate of flow of carbon dioxide was kept constant during the runs.

The results given above are also in agreement with the findings of Hedden³, who has shown that a coke labelled as 'Special Foundry Coke' has a higher reactivity towards carbon dioxide than other metallurgical cokes.

The foregoing does not exclude the possibility that reactivity may be important under extreme conditions. The experimental results of Blayden, Noble and Riley⁴, do show evidence of higher hearth temperatures when highly graphitised, and presumably, therefore, very unreactive materials, such as electrode carbon, are used in cupolas. On the other hand, Worner and Evans⁵, and Higgins and Kennedy⁶ find that in a cupola highly reactive carbonised brown-coal briquettes fail to achieve metal temperatures comparable to those obtained with German metallurgical cokes under the same conditions.

However, such extreme cases apart, the above considerations lead to the conclusions, that with metallurgical cokes such as are normally used in practice, reactivity has no major direct influence on the efficiency of cupola operation.

** The work was carried out whilst the author was a Senior Research Officer (Fellow) at the Mineral Chemistry Division of Coal Research, C.S.I.R.O., Chatswood, N.S.W.

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Differential Thermal Analysis of Some Fluoroberyllates

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THERMAL decomposition of sulphates has been investigated^{1,2}. Little seems to have been done on the thermal decomposition of fluoroberyllates. Since chemically they are similar it would be interesting to investigate the thermal decomposition of the fluoroberyllates. The following salts were taken for analysis:

(a) Copper fluoroberyllate, (b) Nickel fluoroberyllate, (c) Cobalt fluoroberyllate, (d) Potassium fluoroberyllate, (e) Aniline Fluoroberyllate.

All the metal fluoroberyllates contain water of crystallisation which are given up on heating. The aniline fluoroberyllate probably decomposes forming CO_2 , H_2O , HF and BeF_2 .

It was previously ascertained that hydrofluoric acid is not evolved when these salts are heated below 200°C.

Experimental

Apparatus used was a Deltatherm Model D200 (Philips Electronics Instruments Company). Heating rates varied from 2°/min to 16.75°/min. All runs were on samples (100–150 mg) against alumina as reference. The sample and reference material were contained in platinum crucibles (8 mm diam \times 10 mm depth) with a central recess.

The sample temperature (T) was measured from the sample thermocouple.

Preparation of metal fluoroberyllates: The metal fluoroberyllates were prepared by dissolving the respective carbonates in calculated amounts of fluoroberyllic acid. The solutions were filtered and kept in vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and allowed to crystallise. The crystals were filtered off into sintered porcelain crucibles, washed twice with ice-cold water and once with 95% ethyl alcohol. After air drying for several hours the crystals were ground to fine powder and were then ready for use.